

Inequivalence of Polynomial and Non-Polynomial Complexity Classes

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Abstract. We give the full proof of inequivalence of P and NP complexity classes which can be addressed to the famous “P versus NP” theorem by Stephen Cook, our approach summarizes all the results obtained before in our prior research of this topic and its failure during the decades of its first appearance in the scientific press.

Keywords: computational complexity, P versus NP, proof, inequivalence.

Introduction. As it was stated before the “P versus NP” question has a long-standing history in the theory of Computational Complexity and Mathematics as well [1], where the symbol of infinity isn’t defined as operand due to the inconvenience of its relation to the operands in the mathematical expression in the algebra of numbers [2].

Thus, by showing that P equals NP we still cannot devise the relation in this algebra, however, if P not equals NP, we can proceed further with the modern aspects.

Before [3] we have shown that there’s a functional relation between complexity classes, i.e. there could exist the function $f(x)$, so that $f(P) = NP$.

We will proceed to the above publication further and give the strict proof of inequivalence of complexity classes and as it follows from this proof the hierarchy of classes which give consolidated proof of the relations between the variety of complexity classes in Computer Science and Theory of Computation [4].

Before our research the Theory of Complexity was well underlined [5] and it follows that first we have to postulate and only then give the question of the relation between complexity classes, basically polynomial “P” and non-polynomial “NP” classes.

Proof. From [3] we have devised the parallel computing law as follows:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{NP}{N} = P.$$

Let’s assume that the above law is correct according to the number of threads N, which operate on a Non-deterministic Turing Machine (NDTM). Also let’s assume that $P = NP$, then it follows:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} = 1 \Rightarrow 0 = 1 \Rightarrow P \neq NP.$$

The output above demonstrates the simplest way of proving the inequivalence of complexity classes according to the parallel computing law.

Conclusion. We have shown the inequivalence of complexity classes around our final proof which is given as a final contribution to the field of Computational Complexity.

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References

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